

Double-Digit Cyclic-Type Bordered Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 20

The whole work is also available at author's sites:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17009>

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*This work brings **double-digit cyclic-type** algebraic magic squares of orders 7 to 20 for **reduced entries**. By **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These entries are non-sequential positive and negative numbers. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe decimal or fractional values of the entries depending on the types of magic squares. The idea of double-digit [30] is applied to bring these of magic squares. Moreover, we have considered the magic rectangles in a cyclic way, i.e, all the four side in each case are of equal sums in widths and lengths. For similar kind of work for different orders in different styles and ways, the readers are suggested to see author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21].*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).

E-mail: ijaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA

Contents

1 Introduction	3
2 Double-Digit Algebraic magic squares	3
2.1 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 7	5
2.2 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 8	6
2.3 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 9	7
2.4 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 10	9
2.5 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 11	10
2.6 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 12	12
2.7 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 13	14
2.8 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 14	16
2.9 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 15	18
2.10 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 16	20
2.11 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 17	22
2.12 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 18	25
2.13 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 19	28
2.14 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 20	31
3 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers	34

1 Introduction

This work brings **double-digit** or **double-layer algebraic** magic squares of orders 7 to 20 for reduced entries. Sometimes, these types of magic squares, we call as self-made, because they are complete in themselves. Just choose the entries and magic sum, we always get a magic square.

We know that magic sum of a magic square of order n having 1 to n^2 number of entries is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}$$

In this work the entries are written as variables and their combinations. The work is based on the four equal sums magic rectangles in each border with width as 2. The size of the length the magic rectangle depends on the orders of the magic squares. For simplicity, these types of magic squares we call as **cyclic-type**. Similar kind of study for the different styles and orders refer author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. For **double-digit** work for **sequential** entries refer [24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

2 Double-Digit Algebraic magic squares

The section bring results and examples of **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares complete in itself for the orders 7 to 20. These are based on equal sums magic rectangles of equal width. For our study we shall make use of **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares of orders 3, 4, 5 and 6. These are given as follows.

Result 2.1. A magic square of order 3 with **reduced entries algebraic** is given by

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$
$A1$	$A2$	$M-A1-A2$

• Details

Knowing only two entries $A1$ and $A2$ and the magic sum M , we can construct a magic square of order 3. To avoid decimal entries, we must always consider the magic sum as a multiple of 3. This magic square can seen in the web-site of F. Gaspalou [3].

Result 2.2. Let's consider the following magic square of order 4

$A1$	$M+A4-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	$A3$
$A6$	$A4$	$A5$	$M-A4-A5-A6$
$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$
$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	$A2$

• **Details**

It is a magic square of order 4 for reduced entries. The letter *S* represents the magic sum of order 4. This magic square is also due to F. Gaspalou [3].

Result 2.3. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4
A9-A2+A8	A6	A1+A2+A3+A4-A6-A7-A8	A7	S-A1-A3-A4-A9
A2+A3+A4-A6-A8	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A7-A9	A8	A8-A2-A3+A6+A9	A1+A2+A3-A7-A8
A8-A3+A6	A1-A7+A9	A2+A3-A8	S-A1-A6-A8-A9	A8-A2+A7
S-A1-A4-A8-A9	A3+A4-A6	A8-A2-A3+A6+A7	A1+A2-A7	A9

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 with reduced entries. The letter *M* represents the magic sum of order 5. This magic square can be seen in F. Gaspalou [3] web-site. See below two examples.

Result 2.4. Let's consider a following magic square of order 6 with reduced entries:

$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$a3+a4-S/3$	$2*S/3-a4$	$2*S/3-a3$
$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a3-a4$	$S/3$	$2*a3+a4-2*S/3$
$a1$	$a2$	$S-a1-a2$	$a3$	$a4$	$S-a3-a4$
$a5+a6-S/3$	$2*S/3-a6$	$2*S/3-a5$	$a7+a8-S/3$	$2*S/3-a8$	$2*S/3-a7$
$4*S/3-2*a5-a6$	$S/3$	$2*a5+a6-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a7-a8$	$S/3$	$2*a7+a8-2*S/3$
$a5$	$a6$	$S-a5-a6$	$a7$	$a8$	$S-a7-a8$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic** magic square of order 6 for reduced entries. It is constructed based on four equal sums **magic squares** order 3. The letter *S* represents the magic sum of order 3.

We shall frequently use these for magic square in our work based on magic rectangles. These four magic squares shall also be in the middle of the magic square. Magic squares of orders 3, 4 and 5 can be seen in F. Gaspalou’s site [3]. The work on order 6 is given by the author [14, 15].

2.1 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 7

Result 2.5. *Let’s consider a following magic square of order 7 with reduced entries:*

a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	$(5/3)*S-a_3-a_4-a_5-a_6$	$(2/3)*S-a_7$	a_7
$(2/3)*S-a_3$	$(2/3)*S-a_4$	$(2/3)*S-a_5$	$(2/3)*S-a_6$	$a_3+a_4+a_5+a_6-S$	$(2/3)*S-a_8$	a_8
$(5/3)*S+a_7-a_8-2*a_{14}-a_{15}-a_{16}$	$a_8+2*a_{14}+a_{15}+a_{16}-S-a_7$	$a_1+a_2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_2$	$2*S/3-a_1$	$(2/3)*S-a_9$	a_9
a_{16}	$(2/3)*S-a_{16}$	$4*S/3-2*a_1-a_2$	$S/3$	$2*a_1+a_2-2*S/3$	$(2/3)*S-a_{10}$	a_{10}
a_{15}	$(2/3)*S-a_{15}$	a_1	a_2	$S-a_1-a_2$	$a_7+a_8+a_9+a_{10}-S$	$(5/3)*S-a_7-a_8-a_9-a_{10}$
a_{14}	$(2/3)*S-a_{14}$	$a_4+2*a_{11}+a_{12}+a_{13}-S-a_3$	$(2/3)*S-a_{13}$	$(2/3)*S-a_{12}$	$(2/3)*S-a_{11}$	$(2/3)*S+a_3-a_4-a_{11}$
$a_8+a_{14}-a_7$	$(2/3)*S+a_7-a_8-a_{14}$	$(5/3)*S+a_3-a_4-2*a_{11}-a_{12}-a_{13}$	a_{13}	a_{12}	a_{11}	$a_4+a_{11}-a_3$

• Details

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 embedded with a magic square of order 3. Since the magic square of order 3 requires magic sum as multiple of 3, otherwise we have decimal entries, then the magic sum of order 7 is also multiple of 3. The magic sum of order 7 is given as $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$, where S is the magic sum of order 3.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.5.

Example 2.1. *Let’s consider following two examples based on the Result 2.5:*

7	mgc							49	7	mgc							56		
		12	13	14	15	-19	-2	16	49			12	13	14	15	-14	0	16	56
		2	1	0	-1	33	-3	17	49			4	3	2	1	30	-1	17	56
		-61	75	14	3	4	-4	18	49			-56	72	13	5	6	-2	18	56
		25	-11	-3	7	17	-5	19	49			25	-9	1	8	15	-3	19	56
		24	-10	10	11	0	49	-35	49			24	-8	10	11	3	46	-30	56
		23	-9	63	-8	-7	-6	-7	49			23	-7	60	-6	-5	-4	-5	56
		24	-10	-49	22	21	20	21	49			24	-8	-44	22	21	20	21	56
		49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49			56	56	56	56	56	56	56	56

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 21$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := 49$.
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 24$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := 56$.

2.2 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 8

Result 2.6. Let's consider a following magic square of order 8 with reduced entries:

a7	a8	a9	a10	a11	$(3/2)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11$	$S/2-a12$	a12
$S/2-a7$	$S/2-a8$	$S/2-a9$	$S/2-a10$	$S/2-a11$	$a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-S$	$S/2-a13$	a13
$(3/2)*S-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a12-a13$	$a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a12+a13-S$	a1	$a4+S-a6-a1$	$a6-a3-a4$	a3	$S/2-a14$	a14
a24	$S/2-a24$	a6	a4	a5	$S-a4-a5-a6$	$S/2-a15$	a15
a23	$S/2-a23$	$a2+a3-a6$	$a1+a2-a5$	$S-a1-a2-a4$	$a4+a5+a6-a2-a3$	$S/2-a16$	a16
a22	$S/2-a22$	$S-a1-a2-a3$	$a5-a2-2*a4+a6$	$a1+a2+a3+2*a4-a5-a6$	a2	$a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-S$	$(3/2)*S-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16$
a21	$S/2-a21$	$a20+a19+a18+2*a17-a7+a8-S$	$S/2-a20$	$S/2-a19$	$S/2-a18$	$S/2-a17$	$(1/2)*S+a7-a8-a17$
$a13+a21-a12$	$(1/2)*S+a12-a13-a21$	$(3/2)*S-a20-a19-a18-2*a17+a7-a8$	a20	a19	a18	a17	$a8+a17-a7$

• Details

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 embedded with a magic square of order 4. Since the magic square of order 4 requires magic sum as multiple of 2, otherwise we have decimal entries, then the magic sum of order 8 is also

multiple of 2. The magic sum of order 8 is given as $S_{8 \times 8} := 2S$, where S is the magic sum of order 4.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.6.

Example 2.2. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.6:

8	mgc									52		8	mgc									68
		16	17	18	19	20	-51	-8	21	52			16	17	18	19	20	-39	-4	21	68	
		-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	64	-9	22	52			1	0	-1	-2	-3	56	-5	22	68	
		-118	131	10	14	-10	12	-10	23	52			-106	123	10	22	-10	12	-6	23	68	
		33	-20	15	13	14	-16	-11	24	52			33	-16	15	13	14	-8	-7	24	68	
		32	-19	8	7	-8	19	-12	25	52			32	-15	8	7	0	19	-8	25	68	
		31	-18	-7	-8	30	11	89	-76	52			31	-14	1	-8	30	11	81	-64	68	
		30	-17	111	-16	-15	-14	-13	-14	52			30	-13	103	-12	-11	-10	-9	-10	68	
		31	-18	-98	29	28	27	26	27	52			31	-14	-86	29	28	27	26	27	68	
		52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52			68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 26$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 52$.
- Second example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 34$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 68$.

2.3 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 9

Result 2.7. Let's consider a following magic square of order 9 with reduced entries:

a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	$(7/5)*S-a9-a10-a11-a12-a13-a14$	$2*S/5-a15$	a15
$2*S/5-a9$	$2*S/5-a10$	$2*S/5-a11$	$2*S/5-a12$	$2*S/5-a13$	$2*S/5-a14$	$a9+a10+a11+a12+a13+a14-S$	$2*S/5-a16$	a16
$(7/5)*S-a30-a29-a28-a27-2*a26+a15-a16$	$a30+a29+a28+a27+2*a26-a15+a16-S$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4$	a3	a4	$2*S/5-a17$	a17
a30	$2*S/5-a30$	$a8-a2+a7$	a5	$a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-a7$	a6	$S-a1-a3-a4-a8$	$2*S/5-a18$	a18
a29	$2*S/5-a29$	$a2+a3+a4-a5-a7$	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a8$	a7	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a8$	$a1+a2+a3-a6-a7$	$2*S/5-a19$	a19
a28	$2*S/5-a28$	$a7-a3+a5$	$a1-a6+a8$	$a2+a3-a7$	$S-a1-a5-a7-a8$	$a7-a2+a6$	$2*S/5-a20$	a20
a27	$2*S/5-a27$	$S-a1-a4-a7-a8$	$a3+a4-a5$	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a6$	$a1+a2-a6$	a8	$a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-S$	$(7/5)*S-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$
a26	$2*S/5-a26$	$a25+a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a9+a10-S$	$2*S/5-a25$	$2*S/5-a24$	$2*S/5-a23$	$2*S/5-a22$	$2*S/5-a21$	$(2/5)*S+a9-a10-a21$
$a16+a26-a15$	$(2/5)*S+a15-a16-a26$	$(7/5)*S-a25-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a9-a10$	a25	a24	a23	a22	a21	$a10+a21-a9$

• **Details**

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. Here the magic sum of order 5 don't have any condition, but the magic sum of order 9 depends on number 5, i.e., $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$, where S is the magic sum of order 5. This requires the magic sum of order 9 should be multiple of 5, otherwise we may have decimal entries.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.7.

Example 2.3. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.7:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/							©IJT	81	
		19	20	21	22	23	24	-66	-7	25	81
		-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	84	-8	26	81
		-164	182	11	12	-5	13	14	-9	27	81
		40	-22	23	15	2	16	-11	-10	28	81
		39	-21	7	-7	17	25	3	-11	29	81
		38	-20	19	13	8	-16	21	-12	30	81
		37	-19	-15	12	23	7	18	120	-102	81
		36	-18	152	-17	-16	-15	-14	-13	-14	81
		37	-19	-134	35	34	33	32	31	32	81
		81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/							©IJT	90	
		19	20	21	22	23	24	-59	-5	25	90
		1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	79	-6	26	90
		-157	177	11	12	0	13	14	-7	27	90
		40	-20	23	15	2	16	-6	-8	28	90
		39	-19	7	-2	17	25	3	-9	29	90
		38	-18	19	13	8	-11	21	-10	30	90
		37	-17	-10	12	23	7	18	115	-95	90
		36	-16	147	-15	-14	-13	-12	-11	-12	90
		37	-17	-127	35	34	33	32	31	32	90
		90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{5 \times 5} := 45$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := 81$.
- Second example: $S_{5 \times 5} := 50$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := 90$.

2.4 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 10

Result 2.8. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:*

a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	a15	$(8/3)*S-a9-a10-a11-a12-a13-a14-a15$	$(2/3)*S-a16$	a16
$(2/3)*S-a9$	$(2/3)*S-a10$	$(2/3)*S-a11$	$(2/3)*S-a12$	$(2/3)*S-a13$	$(2/3)*S-a14$	$(2/3)*S-a15$	$a9+a10+a11+a12+a13+a14+a15-2*S$	$(2/3)*S-a17$	a17
$(8/3)*S-a34-a33-a32-a31-a30-2*a29+a16-a17$	$a34+a33+a32+a31+a30+2*a29-a16+a17-2*S$	$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$a3+a4-S/3$	$2*S/3-a4$	$2*S/3-a3$	$(2/3)*S-a18$	a18
a34	$(2/3)*S-a34$	$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a3-a4$	$S/3$	$2*a3+a4-2*S/3$	$(2/3)*S-a19$	a19
a33	$(2/3)*S-a33$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2$	a3	a4	$S-a3-a4$	$(2/3)*S-a20$	a20
a32	$(2/3)*S-a32$	$a5+a6-S/3$	$2*S/3-a6$	$2*S/3-a5$	$a7+a8-S/3$	$2*S/3-a8$	$2*S/3-a7$	$(2/3)*S-a21$	a21
a31	$(2/3)*S-a31$	$4*S/3-2*a5-a6$	$S/3$	$2*a5+a6-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a7-a8$	$S/3$	$2*a7+a8-2*S/3$	$(2/3)*S-a22$	a22
a30	$(2/3)*S-a30$	a5	a6	$S-a5-a6$	a7	a8	$S-a7-a8$	$a16+a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22-2*S$	$(8/3)*S-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22$
a29	$(2/3)*S-a29$	$a28+a27+a26+a25+a24+2*a23-a9+a10-2*S$	$(2/3)*S-a28$	$(2/3)*S-a27$	$(2/3)*S-a26$	$(2/3)*S-a25$	$(2/3)*S-a24$	$(2/3)*S-a23$	$(2/3)*S+a9-a10-a23$
$a17+a29-a16$	$(2/3)*S+a16-a17-a29$	$(8/3)*S-a28-a27-a26-a25-a24-2*a23+a9-a10$	a28	a27	a26	a25	a24	a23	$a10+a23-a9$

• Details

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is again composed of four equal sums magic squares of order 3. Since the magic square of order 3 requires magic sum as multiple of 3, otherwise we have decimal entries, then the magic sum of order 10 is also a multiple of 3. The magic sum of order 10 is given as $S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10S}{3}$, where S is the magic sum of order 3. In this case the magic sum of order 6 is given as $S_{6 \times 6} := 2S$.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.8.

Example 2.4. *Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.8:*

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										150
18	19	20	21	22	23	24	-27	5	25	150		
12	11	10	9	8	7	6	57	4	26	150		
-162	192	6	19	20	10	17	18	3	27	150		
43	-13	29	15	1	23	15	7	2	28	150		
42	-12	10	11	24	12	13	20	1	29	150		
41	-11	14	15	16	18	13	14	0	30	150		
40	-10	17	15	13	11	15	19	-1	31	150		
39	-9	14	15	16	16	17	12	106	-76	150		
38	-8	150	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-3	150		
39	-9	-120	37	36	35	34	33	32	33	150		
150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150		

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
18	19	20	21	22	23	24	-19	7	25	160		
14	13	12	11	10	9	8	51	6	26	160		
-154	186	5	21	22	9	19	20	5	27	160		
43	-11	33	16	-1	27	16	5	4	28	160		
42	-10	10	11	27	12	13	23	3	29	160		
41	-9	13	17	18	17	15	16	2	30	160		
40	-8	21	16	11	15	16	17	1	31	160		
39	-7	14	15	19	16	17	15	100	-68	160		
38	-6	144	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	-1	160		
39	-7	-112	37	36	35	34	33	32	33	160		
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160		

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 45$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 90$ and $S_{10 \times 10} := 150$
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 48$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 96$ and $S_{10 \times 10} := 160$.

2.5 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 11

Result 2.9. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 11 with reduced entries:*

a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	$3*S-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24$	$(2/3)*S-a25$	a25
$(2/3)*S-a17$	$(2/3)*S-a18$	$(2/3)*S-a19$	$(2/3)*S-a20$	$(2/3)*S-a21$	$(2/3)*S-a22$	$(2/3)*S-a23$	$(2/3)*S-a24$	$a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22+a23+a24-(7/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a26$	a26
$3*S-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-2*a41+a25-a26$	$a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+2*a41-a25+a26-(7/3)*S$	a3	a4	a5	a6	$(5/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6$	$(2/3)*S-a7$	a7	$(2/3)*S-a27$	a27
a47	$(2/3)*S-a47$	$(2/3)*S-a3$	$(2/3)*S-a4$	$(2/3)*S-a5$	$(2/3)*S-a6$	$a3+a4+a5+a6-S$	$(2/3)*S-a8$	a8	$(2/3)*S-a28$	a28
a46	$(2/3)*S-a46$	$(5/3)*S+a7-a8-2*a14-a15-a16$	$a8+2*a14+a15+a16-S-a7$	$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$(2/3)*S-a9$	a9	$(2/3)*S-a29$	a29
a45	$(2/3)*S-a45$	a16	$(2/3)*S-a16$	$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$(2/3)*S-a10$	a10	$(2/3)*S-a30$	a30
a44	$(2/3)*S-a44$	a15	$(2/3)*S-a15$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2$	$a7+a8+a9+a10-S$	$(5/3)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10$	$(2/3)*S-a31$	a31
a43	$(2/3)*S-a43$	a14	$(2/3)*S-a14$	$a4+2*a11+a12+a13-S-a3$	$(2/3)*S-a13$	$(2/3)*S-a12$	$(2/3)*S-a11$	$(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a11$	$(2/3)*S-a32$	a32
a42	$(2/3)*S-a42$	$a8+a14-a7$	$(2/3)*S+a7-a8-a14$	$(5/3)*S+a3-a4-2*a11-a12-a13$	a13	a12	a11	$a4+a11-a3$	$a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32-(7/3)*S$	$3*S-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32$
a41	$(2/3)*S-a41$	$a39+a38+a37+a36+a35+a34+2*a33-a17+a18-(7/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a39$	$(2/3)*S-a38$	$(2/3)*S-a37$	$(2/3)*S-a36$	$(2/3)*S-a35$	$(2/3)*S-a34$	$(2/3)*S-a33$	$(2/3)*S+a17-a18-a33$
$a26+a41-a25$	$(2/3)*S+a25-a26-a41$	$3*S-a39-a38-a37-a36-a35-a34-2*a33+a17-a18$	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	$a18+a33-a17$

• **Details**

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×9 (equality in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 3. Since the magic square of order 3 requires magic sum as multiple of 3, otherwise we have decimal entries, then the magic sums of orders 7 and 11 are also multiples of 3. The magic sum of orders 7 and 11 are given as $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$ and $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$, where S is the magic sum of order 3.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.9.

Example 2.5. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.9:

11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										121	11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										143		
		18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	-73	-4	26	121			18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	-55	0	26	143
		4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	95	-5	27	121			8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	81	-1	27	143
		-259	281	4	5	6	7	33	14	8	-6	28	121			-241	267	4	5	6	7	43	18	8	-2	28	143
		48	-26	18	17	16	15	-11	13	9	-7	29	121			48	-22	22	21	20	19	-17	17	9	-3	29	143
		47	-25	-9	31	-6	19	20	12	10	-8	30	121			47	-21	1	25	-8	23	24	16	10	-4	30	143
		46	-24	17	5	37	11	-15	11	11	-9	31	121			46	-20	17	9	45	13	-19	15	11	-5	31	143
		45	-23	16	6	2	3	28	5	17	-10	32	121			45	-19	16	10	2	3	34	-1	27	-6	32	143
		44	-22	15	7	19	8	9	10	9	-11	33	121			44	-18	15	11	13	12	13	14	13	-7	33	143
		43	-21	16	6	3	14	13	12	13	159	-137	121			43	-17	16	10	13	14	13	12	13	145	-119	143
		42	-20	217	-18	-17	-16	-15	-14	-13	-12	-13	121			42	-16	203	-14	-13	-12	-11	-10	-9	-8	-9	143
		43	-21	-195	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	121			43	-17	-177	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	143
		121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121			143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 33$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 77$ and $S_{11 \times 11} := 121$
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 39$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 91$ and $S_{11 \times 11} := 143$.

2.6 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 12

Result 2.10. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 12 with reduced entries:*

a25	a26	a27	a28	a29	a30	a31	a32	a33	$(5/2)*S-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33$	S/2-a34	a34
S/2-a25	S/2-a26	S/2-a27	S/2-a28	S/2-a29	S/2-a30	S/2-a31	S/2-a32	S/2-a33	$a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33-2*S$	S/2-a35	a35
$(5/2)*S-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-2*a51+a34-a35$	$a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+2*a51-a34+a35-2*S$	a7	a8	a9	a10	a11	$(3/2)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11$	S/2-a12	a12	S/2-a36	a36
a58	S/2-a58	S/2-a7	S/2-a8	S/2-a9	S/2-a10	S/2-a11	$a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-S$	S/2-a13	a13	S/2-a37	a37
a57	S/2-a57	$(3/2)*S-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a12-a13$	$a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a12+a13-S$	a1	$a4+S-a6-a1$	$a6-a3-a4$	a3	S/2-a14	a14	S/2-a38	a38
a56	S/2-a56	a24	S/2-a24	a6	a4	a5	$S-a4-a5-a6$	S/2-a15	a15	S/2-a39	a39
a55	S/2-a55	a23	S/2-a23	$a2+a3-a6$	$a1+a2-a5$	$S-a1-a2-a4$	$a4+a5+a6-a2-a3$	S/2-a16	a16	S/2-a40	a40
a54	S/2-a54	a22	S/2-a22	$S-a1-a2-a3$	$a5-a2-2*a4+a6$	$a1+a2+a3+2*a4-a5-a6$	a2	$a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-S$	$(3/2)*S-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16$	S/2-a41	a41
a53	S/2-a53	a21	S/2-a21	$a20+a19+a18+2*a17-a7+a8-S$	S/2-a20	S/2-a19	S/2-a18	S/2-a17	$(1/2)*S+a7-a8-a17$	S/2-a42	a42
a52	S/2-a52	$a13+a21-a12$	$(1/2)*S+a12-a13-a21$	$(3/2)*S-a20-a19-a18-2*a17+a7-a8$	a20	a19	a18	a17	$a8+a17-a7$	$a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a41+a42-2*S$	$(5/2)*S-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a41-a42$
a51	S/2-a51	$a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+2*a43-a25+a26-2*S$	S/2-a50	S/2-a49	S/2-a48	S/2-a47	S/2-a46	S/2-a45	S/2-a44	S/2-a43	$(1/2)*S+a25-a26-a43$
$a35+a51-a34$	$(1/2)*S+a34-a35-a51$	$(5/2)*S-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-2*a43+a25-a26$	a50	a49	a48	a47	a46	a45	a44	a43	$a26+a43-a25$

• **Details**

It is composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×10 (equality in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 4. Since the magic square of order 4 requires magic sum as multiple of 2, otherwise we have decimal entries, then the magic sum of order 12 is also multiple of 2. The magic sum of orders 12 and 8 are given as $S_{12 \times 12} := 3S$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 2S$, where S is the magic sum of order 4.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.10

Example 2.6. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.10:

12	mgc	12x12 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											138	12	mgc	12x12 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											156
26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	-155	-12	35	138	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	-140	-9	35	156		
-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	178	-13	36	138	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	166	-10	36	156		
-382	405	8	9	10	11	12	19	10	13	-14	37	138	-367	393	8	9	10	11	12	28	13	13	-11	37	156		
59	-36	15	14	13	12	11	4	9	14	-15	38	138	59	-33	18	17	16	15	14	-2	12	14	-12	38	156		
58	-35	-48	71	2	42	-2	4	8	15	-16	39	138	58	-32	-39	65	2	48	-2	4	11	15	-13	39	156		
57	-34	25	-2	7	5	6	28	7	16	-17	40	138	57	-31	25	1	7	5	6	34	10	16	-14	40	156		
56	-33	24	-1	0	-1	36	11	6	17	-18	41	138	56	-30	24	2	0	-1	42	11	9	17	-15	41	156		
55	-32	23	0	37	0	6	3	29	-6	-19	42	138	55	-29	23	3	43	0	6	3	23	3	-16	42	156		
54	-31	22	1	51	2	3	4	5	4	-20	43	138	54	-28	22	4	45	5	6	7	8	7	-17	43	156		
53	-30	23	0	-28	21	20	19	18	19	259	-236	138	53	-27	23	3	-19	21	20	19	18	19	247	-221	156		
52	-29	333	-28	-27	-26	-25	-24	-23	-22	-21	-22	138	52	-26	321	-25	-24	-23	-22	-21	-20	-19	-18	-19	156		
53	-30	-310	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	45	138	53	-27	-295	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	45	156		
138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156			

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 46$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 92$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 138$
- Second example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 52$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 104$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 156$.

2.7 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 13

Result 2.11. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 13 with reduced entries:*

a31	a32	a33	a34	a35	a36	a37	a38	a39	a40	$(11/5)*S-a31-a32-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a33$	$2*S/5-a41$	a41
$2*S/5-a31$	$2*S/5-a32$	$2*S/5-a33$	$2*S/5-a34$	$2*S/5-a35$	$2*S/5-a36$	$2*S/5-a37$	$2*S/5-a38$	$2*S/5-a39$	$2*S/5-a40$	$a31+a32+a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a33-(9/5)*S$	$2*S/5-a42$	a42
$(11/5)*S+a41-a42-2*a60-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a61$	$a42+2*a60-a41+a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a61-(9/5)*S$	a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	$(7/5)*S-a9-a10-a11-a12-a13-a14$	$2*S/5-a15$	a15	$2*S/5-a43$	a43
a68	$2*S/5-a68$	$2*S/5-a9$	$2*S/5-a10$	$2*S/5-a11$	$2*S/5-a12$	$2*S/5-a13$	$2*S/5-a14$	$a9+a10+a11+a12+a13+a14-S$	$2*S/5-a16$	a16	$2*S/5-a44$	a44
a67	$2*S/5-a67$	$(7/5)*S-a30-a29-a28-a27-2*a26+a15-a16$	$a30+a29+a28+a27+2*a26-a15+a16-S$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4$	a3	a4	$2*S/5-a17$	a17	$2*S/5-a45$	a45
a66	$2*S/5-a66$	a30	$2*S/5-a30$	$a8-a2+a7$	a5	$a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-a7$	a6	$S-a1-a3-a4-a8$	$2*S/5-a18$	a18	$2*S/5-a46$	a46
a65	$2*S/5-a65$	a29	$2*S/5-a29$	$a2+a3+a4-a5-a7$	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a8$	a7	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a8$	$a1+a2+a3-a6-a7$	$2*S/5-a19$	a19	$2*S/5-a47$	a47
a64	$2*S/5-a64$	a28	$2*S/5-a28$	$a7-a3+a5$	$a1-a6+a8$	$a2+a3-a7$	$S-a1-a5-a7-a8$	$a7-a2+a6$	$2*S/5-a20$	a20	$2*S/5-a48$	a48
a63	$2*S/5-a63$	a27	$2*S/5-a27$	$S-a1-a4-a7-a8$	$a3+a4-a5$	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a6$	$a1+a2-a6$	a8	$a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-S$	$(7/5)*S-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$	$2*S/5-a49$	a49
a62	$2*S/5-a62$	a26	$2*S/5-a26$	$a25+a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a9+a10-S$	$2*S/5-a25$	$2*S/5-a24$	$2*S/5-a23$	$2*S/5-a22$	$2*S/5-a21$	$(2/5)*S+a9-a10-a21$	$2*S/5-a50$	a50
a61	$2*S/5-a61$	$a16+a26-a15$	$(2/5)*S+a15-a16-a26$	$(7/5)*S-a25-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a9-a10$	a25	a24	a23	a22	a21	$a10+a21-a9$	$a42+a41+a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+a43-(9/5)*S$	$(11/5)*S-a42-a41-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43$
a60	$2*S/5-a60$	$a32+2*a51-a31+a52+a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59-(9/5)*S$	$2*S/5-a59$	$2*S/5-a58$	$2*S/5-a57$	$2*S/5-a56$	$2*S/5-a55$	$2*S/5-a54$	$2*S/5-a53$	$2*S/5-a52$	$2*S/5-a51$	$(2/5)*S+a31-a32-a51$
$a42+a60-a41$	$(2/5)*S+a41-a42-a60$	$(11/5)*S+a31-a32-2*a51-a52-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59$	a59	a58	a57	a56	a55	a54	a53	a52	a51	$a32+a51-a31$

• **Details**

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×11 (equality in each case) embedded with a pandiagonal magic square of order 5. The magic square of order 5 don't requires any condition but the magic sums of orders 13 and 9 depends on five, we must have these magic sums as multiples of 5 to avoid decimal entries. The magic sum of orders 13 and 9 are given as $S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13S}{5}$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$, where S is the magic sum of order 5.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.11

Example 2.7. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.11:

13	mgc	13x13 Inder .J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											169	13	mgc	13x13 Inder .J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											182		
	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	-222	-16	42	169		32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	-211	-14	42	182
	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	248	-17	43	169		-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	239	-15	43	182
	-504	530	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	10	16	-18	44	169		-493	521	10	11	12	13	14	15	23	12	16	-16	44	182
	69	-43	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	17	-19	45	169		69	-41	18	17	16	15	14	13	5	11	17	-17	45	182
	68	-42	-82	108	2	3	51	4	5	8	18	-20	46	169		68	-40	-75	103	2	3	56	4	5	10	18	-18	46	182
	67	-41	31	-5	14	6	-7	7	45	7	19	-21	47	169		67	-39	31	-3	14	6	-7	7	50	9	19	-19	47	182
	66	-40	30	-4	-2	49	8	16	-6	6	20	-22	48	169		66	-38	30	-2	-2	54	8	16	-6	8	20	-20	48	182
	65	-39	29	-3	10	4	-1	40	12	5	21	-23	49	169		65	-37	29	-1	10	4	-1	45	12	7	21	-21	49	182
	64	-38	28	-2	41	3	14	-2	9	46	-20	-24	50	169		64	-36	28	0	46	3	14	-2	9	41	-13	-22	50	182
	63	-37	27	-1	78	0	1	2	3	4	3	-25	51	169		63	-35	27	1	73	2	3	4	5	6	5	-23	51	182
	62	-36	28	-2	-52	26	25	24	23	22	23	348	-322	169		62	-34	28	0	-45	26	25	24	23	22	23	339	-311	182
	61	-35	440	-34	-33	-32	-31	-30	-29	-28	-27	-26	-27	169		61	-33	431	-32	-31	-30	-29	-28	-27	-26	-25	-24	-25	182
	62	-36	-414	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	53	169		62	-34	-403	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	53	182
	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{5 \times 5} := 65$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 117$ and $S_{13 \times 13} := 169$
- Second example: $S_{5 \times 5} := 70$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 126$ and $S_{13 \times 13} := 182$.

2.8 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 14

Result 2.12. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 14 with reduced entries:*

a35	a36	a37	a38	a39	a40	a41	a42	a43	a44	a45	$4^*S-a37-a43-a42-a41-a36-a35-a45-a44-a38-a40-a39$	$(2/3)^*S-a46$	a46
$(2/3)^*S-a35$	$(2/3)^*S-a36$	$(2/3)^*S-a37$	$(2/3)^*S-a38$	$(2/3)^*S-a39$	$(2/3)^*S-a40$	$(2/3)^*S-a41$	$(2/3)^*S-a42$	$(2/3)^*S-a43$	$(2/3)^*S-a44$	$(2/3)^*S-a45$	$a37+a43+a42+a41+a36+a35+a45+a44+a38+a40+a39-(10/3)^*S$	$(2/3)^*S-a47$	a47
$4^*S-a73-a71-a69-a70-a72-a74-a75+a46-a47-2^*a67-a68-a76$	$a73+a71+a69+a70+a72+a74+a75+a47+2^*a67-a46+a68+a76-(10/3)^*S$	a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	a15	$(8/3)^*S-a9-a10-a11-a12-a13-a14-a15$	$(2/3)^*S-a16$	a16	$(2/3)^*S-a48$	a48
a76	$(2/3)^*S-a76$	$(2/3)^*S-a9$	$(2/3)^*S-a10$	$(2/3)^*S-a11$	$(2/3)^*S-a12$	$(2/3)^*S-a13$	$(2/3)^*S-a14$	$(2/3)^*S-a15$	$a9+a10+a11+a12+a13+a14+a15-5-2^*S$	$(2/3)^*S-a17$	a17	$(2/3)^*S-a49$	a49
a75	$(2/3)^*S-a75$	$(8/3)^*S-a34-a33-a32-a31-a30-2^*a29+a16-a17$	$a34+a33+a32+a31+a30+2^*a29-a16+a17-2^*S$	$a1+a2-S/3$	$2^*S/3-a2$	$2^*S/3-a1$	$a3+a4-S/3$	$2^*S/3-a4$	$2^*S/3-a3$	$(2/3)^*S-a18$	a18	$(2/3)^*S-a50$	a50
a74	$(2/3)^*S-a74$	a34	$(2/3)^*S-a34$	$4^*S/3-2^*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2^*a1+a2-2^*S/3$	$4^*S/3-2^*a3-a4$	$S/3$	$2^*a3+a4-2^*S/3$	$(2/3)^*S-a19$	a19	$(2/3)^*S-a51$	a51
a73	$(2/3)^*S-a73$	a33	$(2/3)^*S-a33$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2$	a3	a4	$S-a3-a4$	$(2/3)^*S-a20$	a20	$(2/3)^*S-a52$	a52
a72	$(2/3)^*S-a72$	a32	$(2/3)^*S-a32$	$a5+a6-S/3$	$2^*S/3-a6$	$2^*S/3-a5$	$a7+a8-S/3$	$2^*S/3-a8$	$2^*S/3-a7$	$(2/3)^*S-a21$	a21	$(2/3)^*S-a53$	a53
a71	$(2/3)^*S-a71$	a31	$(2/3)^*S-a31$	$4^*S/3-2^*a5-a6$	$S/3$	$2^*a5+a6-2^*S/3$	$4^*S/3-2^*a7-a8$	$S/3$	$2^*a7+a8-2^*S/3$	$(2/3)^*S-a22$	a22	$(2/3)^*S-a54$	a54
a70	$(2/3)^*S-a70$	a30	$(2/3)^*S-a30$	a5	a6	$S-a5-a6$	a7	a8	$S-a7-a8$	$a16+a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22-2^*S$	$(8/3)^*S-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22$	$(2/3)^*S-a55$	a55
a69	$(2/3)^*S-a69$	a29	$(2/3)^*S-a29$	$a28+a27+a26+a25+a24+2^*a23-a9+a10-2^*S$	$(2/3)^*S-a28$	$(2/3)^*S-a27$	$(2/3)^*S-a26$	$(2/3)^*S-a25$	$(2/3)^*S-a24$	$(2/3)^*S-a23$	$(2/3)^*S+a9-a10-a23$	$(2/3)^*S-a56$	a56
a68	$(2/3)^*S-a68$	$a17+a29-a16$	$(2/3)^*S+a16-a17-a29$	$(8/3)^*S-a28-a27-a26-a25-a24-2^*a23+a9-a10$	a28	a27	a26	a25	a24	a23	$a10+a23-a9$	$a51+a50+a46+a53+a52+a49+a48+a47+a56+a55+a54-4-(10/3)^*S$	$4^*S-a51-a50-a46-a53-a52-a49-a48-a47-a56-a55-a54$
a67	$(2/3)^*S-a67$	$a65+a59+a58+a60+a63+a61+a62+a64+a36+2^*a57-a35+a66-(10/3)^*S$	$(2/3)^*S-a66$	$(2/3)^*S-a65$	$(2/3)^*S-a64$	$(2/3)^*S-a63$	$(2/3)^*S-a62$	$(2/3)^*S-a61$	$(2/3)^*S-a60$	$(2/3)^*S-a59$	$(2/3)^*S-a58$	$(2/3)^*S-a57$	$(2/3)^*S+a35-a36-a57$
$a47+a67-a46$	$(2/3)^*S+a46-a47-a67$	$4^*S-a65-a59-a58-a60-a63-a61-a62-a64+a35-a36-2^*a57-a66$	a66	a65	a64	a63	a62	a61	a60	a59	a58	a57	$a36+a57-a35$

• **Details**

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×12 (equal in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is again composed of four equal sums magic squares of order 3. Since the magic square of order 3 requires magic sum as multiple of 3, otherwise we may have decimal entries. The magic sums of orders 10 and 14 are also multiple of 3. The magic sum of orders 10 and 14 are given as $S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10S}{3}$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14S}{3}$, where S is the magic sum of order 3. In this case the magic sum of order 6 is given as $S_{6 \times 6} := 2S$.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.12

Example 2.8. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.12:

14 mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/														308	14 mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/														350
35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	-176	-2	46	308	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	-140	4	46	350		
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	220	-3	47	308	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	190	3	47	350		
-519	563	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	92	28	16	-4	48	308	-483	533	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	116	34	16	2	48	350		
76	-32	35	34	33	32	31	30	29	-48	27	17	-5	49	308	76	-26	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	-66	33	17	1	49	350		
75	-31	-43	87	-19	42	43	-15	40	41	26	18	-6	50	308	75	-25	-19	69	-22	48	49	-18	46	47	32	18	0	50	350		
74	-30	34	10	84	22	-40	78	22	-34	25	19	-7	51	308	74	-24	34	16	96	25	-46	90	25	-40	31	19	-1	51	350		
73	-29	33	11	1	2	63	3	4	59	24	20	-8	52	308	73	-23	33	17	1	2	72	3	4	68	30	20	-2	52	350		
72	-28	32	12	-11	38	39	-7	36	37	23	21	-9	53	308	72	-22	32	18	-14	44	45	-10	42	43	29	21	-3	53	350		
71	-27	31	13	72	22	-28	66	22	-22	22	22	-10	54	308	71	-21	31	19	84	25	-34	78	25	-28	28	22	-4	54	350		
70	-26	30	14	5	6	55	7	8	51	1	43	-11	55	308	70	-20	30	20	5	6	64	7	8	60	-17	67	-5	55	350		
69	-25	29	15	45	16	17	18	19	20	21	20	-12	56	308	69	-19	29	21	27	22	23	24	25	26	27	26	-6	56	350		
68	-24	30	14	-1	28	27	26	25	24	23	24	341	-297	308	68	-18	30	20	23	28	27	26	25	24	23	24	311	-261	350		
67	-23	453	-22	-21	-20	-19	-18	-17	-16	-15	-14	-13	-14	308	67	-17	423	-16	-15	-14	-13	-12	-11	-10	-9	-8	-7	-8	350		
68	-24	-409	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	58	308	68	-18	-373	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	58	350		
308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350			

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 66$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 132$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 220$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := 108$.
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 75$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 150$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 250$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := 350$.

2.9 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 15

Result 2.13. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 15 with reduced entries:*

a48	a49	a50	a51	a52	a53	a54	a55	a56	a57	a58	a59	(13/3)*S-a59-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-a51-a50-a49-a48	(2/3)*S-a60	a60
(2/3)*S-a48	(2/3)*S-a49	(2/3)*S-a50	(2/3)*S-a51	(2/3)*S-a52	(2/3)*S-a53	(2/3)*S-a54	(2/3)*S-a55	(2/3)*S-a56	(2/3)*S-a57	(2/3)*S-a58	(2/3)*S-a59	a59+a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+a51+a50+a49+a48-(11/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a61	a61
(13/3)*S-a92-a93-a89-a90-a91-a88-a84-a85-a86-2*a83+a60-a87-	a92+a93+a89+a90+a91+a88+a84+a85+a86+2*a83-a60+a87+a61-(11/3)*S	a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	3*S-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24	(2/3)*S-a25	a25	(2/3)*S-a62	a62
a93	(2/3)*S-a93	(2/3)*S-a17	(2/3)*S-a18	(2/3)*S-a19	(2/3)*S-a20	(2/3)*S-a21	(2/3)*S-a22	(2/3)*S-a23	(2/3)*S-a24	a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22+a23+a24-(7/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a26	a26	(2/3)*S-a63	a63
a92	(2/3)*S-a92	3*S-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-2*a41+a25-a26	a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+2*a41-a25+a26-(7/3)*S	a3	a4	a5	a6	(5/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6	(2/3)*S-a7	a7	(2/3)*S-a27	a27	(2/3)*S-a64	a64
a91	(2/3)*S-a91	a47	(2/3)*S-a47	(2/3)*S-a3	(2/3)*S-a4	(2/3)*S-a5	(2/3)*S-a6	a3+a4+a5+a6-S	(2/3)*S-a8	a8	(2/3)*S-a28	a28	(2/3)*S-a65	a65
a90	(2/3)*S-a90	a46	(2/3)*S-a46	(5/3)*S+a7-a8-2*a14-a15-a16	a8+2*a14+a15+a16-S-a7	a1+a2-S/3	2*S/3-a2	2*S/3-a1	(2/3)*S-a9	a9	(2/3)*S-a29	a29	(2/3)*S-a66	a66
a89	(2/3)*S-a89	a45	(2/3)*S-a45	a16	(2/3)*S-a16	4*S/3-2*a1-a2	S/3	2*a1+a2-2*S/3	(2/3)*S-a10	a10	(2/3)*S-a30	a30	(2/3)*S-a67	a67
a88	(2/3)*S-a88	a44	(2/3)*S-a44	a15	(2/3)*S-a15	a1	a2	S-a1-a2	a7+a8+a9+a10-S	(5/3)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10	(2/3)*S-a31	a31	(2/3)*S-a68	a68
a87	(2/3)*S-a87	a43	(2/3)*S-a43	a14	(2/3)*S-a14	a4+2*a11+a12+a13-S-a3	(2/3)*S-a13	(2/3)*S-a12	(2/3)*S-a11	(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a11	(2/3)*S-a32	a32	(2/3)*S-a69	a69
a86	(2/3)*S-a86	a42	(2/3)*S-a42	a8+a14-a7	(2/3)*S+a7-a8-a14	(5/3)*S+a3-a4-2*a11-a12-a13	a13	a12	a11	a4+a11-a3	a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32-(7/3)*S	3*S-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32	(2/3)*S-a70	a70
a85	(2/3)*S-a85	a41	(2/3)*S-a41	a39+a38+a37+a36+a35+a34+2*a33-a17+a18-(7/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a39	(2/3)*S-a38	(2/3)*S-a37	(2/3)*S-a36	(2/3)*S-a35	(2/3)*S-a34	(2/3)*S-a33	(2/3)*S+a17-a18-a33	(2/3)*S-a71	a71
a84	(2/3)*S-a84	a26+a41-a25	(2/3)*S+a25-a26-a41	3*S-a39-a38-a37-a36-a35-a34-2*a33+a17-a18	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	a18+a33-a17	a71+a70+a69+a68+a67+a60+a66+a65+a64+a63+a62+a61-(11/3)*S	(13/3)*S-a71-a70-a69-a68-a67-a60-a66-a65-a64-a63-a62-a61
a83	(2/3)*S-a83	2*a72+a73+a74+a75+a76+a77+a78+a79+a80+a81+a82-a48+a49-(11/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a82	(2/3)*S-a81	(2/3)*S-a80	(2/3)*S-a79	(2/3)*S-a78	(2/3)*S-a77	(2/3)*S-a76	(2/3)*S-a75	(2/3)*S-a74	(2/3)*S-a73	(2/3)*S-a72	(2/3)*S+a48-a49-a72
a61+a83-a60	(2/3)*S+a60-a61-a83	(13/3)*S-2*a72-a73-a74-a75-a76-a77-a78-a79-a80-a81-a82+a48-a49	a82	a81	a80	a79	a78	a77	a76	a75	a74	a73	a72	a49+a72-a48

• **Details**

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×12 (equal in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is again composed of four equal sums magic squares of order 3. Since the magic square of order 3 requires magic sum as multiple of 3, otherwise we may have decimal entries. The magic sums of orders 10 and 14 are also multiple of 3. The magic sum of orders 10 and 14 are given as $S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10S}{3}$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14S}{3}$, where S is the magic sum of order 3. In this case the magic sum of order 6 is given as $S_{6 \times 6} := 2S$.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.13

Example 2.9. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.13:

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														315	
		49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-381	-19	61	315
		-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	423	-20	62	315
		-791	833	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	17	16	26	-21	63	315
		94	-52	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	25	15	27	-22	64	315
		93	-51	-169	211	4	5	6	7	83	34	8	14	28	-23	65	315
		92	-50	48	-6	38	37	36	35	-41	33	9	13	29	-24	66	315
		91	-49	47	-5	41	1	-16	39	40	32	10	12	30	-25	67	315
		90	-48	46	-4	17	25	77	21	-35	31	11	11	31	-26	68	315
		89	-47	45	-3	16	26	2	3	58	-25	67	10	32	-27	69	315
		88	-46	44	-2	15	27	-11	28	29	30	29	9	33	-28	70	315
		87	-45	43	-1	16	26	53	14	13	12	13	89	-47	-29	71	315
		86	-44	42	0	147	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	7	-30	72	315
		85	-43	43	-1	-105	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	567	-525	315
		84	-42	701	-41	-40	-39	-38	-37	-36	-35	-34	-33	-32	-31	-32	315
		85	-43	-659	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	74	315
		315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														360	
		49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-342	-13	61	360
		-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	390	-14	62	360
		-752	800	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	44	22	26	-15	63	360
		94	-46	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	4	21	27	-16	64	360
		93	-45	-142	190	4	5	6	7	98	40	8	20	28	-17	65	360
		92	-44	48	0	44	43	42	41	-50	39	9	19	29	-18	66	360
		91	-43	47	1	56	-8	-19	45	46	38	10	18	30	-19	67	360
		90	-42	46	2	17	31	89	24	-41	37	11	17	31	-20	68	360
		89	-41	45	3	16	32	2	3	67	-34	82	16	32	-21	69	360
		88	-40	44	4	15	33	-20	34	35	36	35	15	33	-22	70	360
		87	-39	43	5	16	32	68	14	13	12	13	68	-20	-23	71	360
		86	-38	42	6	126	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	13	-24	72	360
		85	-37	43	5	-78	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	534	-486	360
		84	-36	668	-35	-34	-33	-32	-31	-30	-29	-28	-27	-26	-25	-26	360
		85	-37	-620	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	74	360
		360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 63$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 147$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 231$ and $S_{15 \times 15} := 315$.
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 72$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 168$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 264$ and $S_{15 \times 15} := 360$.

2.10 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 16

Result 2.14. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 16 with reduced entries:*

a59	a60	a61	a62	a63	a64	a65	a66	a67	a68	a69	a70	a71	(7/2)*S-a69-a68-a70-a67-a66-a65-a64-a63-a71-a62-a61-a60-a59	S/2-a72	a72		
S/2-a59	S/2-a60	S/2-a61	S/2-a62	S/2-a63	S/2-a64	S/2-a65	S/2-a66	S/2-a67	S/2-a68	S/2-a69	S/2-a70	S/2-a71	a69+a68+a70+a67+a66+a65+a64+a63+a71+a62+a61+a60+a59-3*S	S/2-a73	a73		
(7/2)*S-a107-a106-a105-a104-a108-a103-a102-a101-a100+a72-a73-2*a97-a98-a99	a107+a106+a105+a104+a108+a103+a102+a101+a100+a73+2*a97-a72+a98+a99-3*S	a25	a26	a27	a28	a29	a30	a31	a32	a33	(5/2)*S-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33	S/2-a34	a34	S/2-a74	a74		
a108	S/2-a108	S/2-a25	S/2-a26	S/2-a27	S/2-a28	S/2-a29	S/2-a30	S/2-a31	S/2-a32	S/2-a33	a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33-2*S	S/2-a35	a35	S/2-a75	a75		
a107	S/2-a107	(5/2)*S-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-2*a51+a34-a35	a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+2*a51-a34+a35-2*S	a7	a8	a9	a10	a11	(3/2)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11	S/2-a12	a12	S/2-a36	a36	S/2-a76	a76		
a106	S/2-a106	a58	S/2-a58	S/2-a7	S/2-a8	S/2-a9	S/2-a10	S/2-a11	a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-S	S/2-a13	a13	S/2-a37	a37	S/2-a77	a77		
a105	S/2-a105	a57	S/2-a57	(3/2)*S-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a12-a13	a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a12+a13-S	a1	a4+S-a6-a1	a6-a3-a4	a3	S/2-a14	a14	S/2-a38	a38	S/2-a78	a78		
a104	S/2-a104	a56	S/2-a56	a24	S/2-a24	a6	a4	a5	S-a4-a5-a6	S/2-a15	a15	S/2-a39	a39	S/2-a79	a79		
a103	S/2-a103	a55	S/2-a55	a23	S/2-a23	a2+a3-a6	a1+a2-a5	S-a1-a2-a4	a4+a5+a6-a2-a3	S/2-a16	a16	S/2-a40	a40	S/2-a80	a80		
a102	S/2-a102	a54	S/2-a54	a22	S/2-a22	S-a1-a2-a3	a5-a2-2*a4+a6	a1+a2+a3+2*a4-a5-a6	a2	a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-S	(3/2)*S-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16	S/2-a41	a41	S/2-a81	a81		
a101	S/2-a101	a53	S/2-a53	a21	S/2-a21	a20+a19+a18+2*a17-a7+a8-S	S/2-a20	S/2-a19	S/2-a18	S/2-a17	(1/2)*S+a7-a8-a17	S/2-a42	a42	S/2-a82	a82		
a100	S/2-a100	a52	S/2-a52	a13+a21-a12	(1/2)*S+a12-a13-a21	(3/2)*S-a20-a19-a18-2*a17+a7-a8	a20	a19	a18	a17	a8+a17-a7	a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a41+a42-2*S	(5/2)*S-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a41-a42	S/2-a83	a83		
a99	S/2-a99	a51	S/2-a51	a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+2*a43-a25+a26-2*S	S/2-a50	S/2-a49	S/2-a48	S/2-a47	S/2-a46	S/2-a45	S/2-a44	S/2-a43	(1/2)*S+a25-a26-a43	S/2-a84	a84		
a98	S/2-a98	a35+a51-a34	(1/2)*S+a34-a35-a51	(5/2)*S-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-2*a43+a25-a26	a50	a49	a48	a47	a46	a45	a44	a43	a26+a43-a25	a80+a81+a82+a83+a84+a79+a78+a73+a74+a75+a76+a77+a72-3*S	(7/2)*S-a80-a81-a82-a83-a84-a79-a78-a73-a74-a75-a76-a77-a72	S/2-a85	(1/2)*S+a59-a60-a85
a97	S/2-a97	a86+a95+a96+a89+a90+a91+a92+a93+a94+a87+a60+2*a85-a59+a88-3*S	S/2-a96	S/2-a95	S/2-a94	S/2-a93	S/2-a92	S/2-a91	S/2-a90	S/2-a89	S/2-a88	S/2-a87	S/2-a86	S/2-a85	(1/2)*S+a59-a60-a85		
a73+a97-a72	(1/2)*S+a72-a73-a97	(7/2)*S-a86-a95-a96-a89-a90-a91-a92-a93-a94-a87+a59-a60-2*a85-a88	a96	a95	a94	a93	a92	a91	a90	a89	a88	a87	a86	a85	a60+a85-a59		

• Details

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×6 , 2×10 and 2×14 (equality in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 4. Since the magic square of order 4 requires magic sum as multiple of 2, otherwise we have decimal entries, then the magic sum of orders, 8, 12 and 16 are also multiple of 2. The magic sum of orders 16, 12 and 8 are given as $S_{16 \times 16} := 4S$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 3S$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 2S$, where S is the magic sum of order 4.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.14

Example 2.10. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.14:

16	mgc	16x16	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	408	16	mgc	16x16	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	440																							
	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	-501	-22	73	408		60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	-473	-18	73	440	
	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	552	-23	74	408		-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	528	-19	74	440	
	-984	1035	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	-15	16	35	-24	75	408		-956	1011	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	5	20	35	-20	75	440	
	109	-58	25	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	66	15	36	-25	76	408		109	-54	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	50	19	36	-21	76	440	
	108	-57	-242	293	8	9	10	11	12	103	38	13	14	37	-26	77	408		108	-53	-222	277	8	9	10	11	12	115	42	13	18	37	-22	77	440	
	107	-56	59	-8	43	42	41	40	39	-52	37	14	13	38	-27	78	408		107	-52	59	-4	47	46	45	44	43	-60	41	14	17	38	-23	78	440	
	106	-55	58	-7	36	15	2	98	-2	4	36	15	12	39	-28	79	408		106	-51	58	-3	48	7	2	106	-2	4	40	15	16	39	-24	79	440	
	105	-54	57	-6	25	26	7	5	6	84	35	16	11	40	-29	80	408		105	-50	57	-2	25	30	7	5	6	92	39	16	15	40	-25	80	440	
	104	-53	56	-5	24	27	0	-1	92	11	34	17	10	41	-30	81	408		104	-49	56	-1	24	31	0	-1	100	11	38	17	14	41	-26	81	440	
	103	-52	55	-4	23	28	93	0	6	3	-27	78	9	42	-31	82	408		103	-48	55	0	23	32	101	0	6	3	-35	90	13	42	-27	82	440	
	102	-51	54	-3	22	29	-5	30	31	32	33	32	8	43	-32	83	408		102	-47	54	1	22	33	-13	34	35	36	37	36	12	43	-28	83	440	
	101	-50	53	-2	23	28	56	21	20	19	18	19	147	-96	-33	84	408		101	-46	53	2	23	32	68	21	20	19	18	19	131	-76	-29	84	440	
	100	-49	52	-1	221	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	6	-34	85	408		100	-45	52	3	205	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	10	-30	85	440	
	99	-48	53	-2	-170	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	45	721	-670	408		99	-44	53	2	-150	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	45	697	-642	440	
	98	-47	879	-46	-45	-44	-43	-42	-41	-40	-39	-38	-37	-36	-35	-36	408		98	-43	855	-42	-41	-40	-39	-38	-37	-36	-35	-34	-33	-32	-31	-32	440	
	99	-48	-828	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	87	408		99	-44	-800	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	87	440	
	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408	408		440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440	440

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 102$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 204$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 312$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 408$.
- Second example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 110$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 220$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 330$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 440$.

2.11 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 17

Result 2.15. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 17 with reduced entries:*

a69	a70	a71	a72	a73	a74	a75	a76	a77	a78	a79	a80	a81	a82	$3^5 \cdot a76 - a74 - a75 - a73 - a72 - a71 - a70 - a69 - a82 - a81 - a80 - a79 - a78 - a77$	$2^5/5 \cdot a83$	a83	
$2^5/5 \cdot a69$	$2^5/5 \cdot a70$	$2^5/5 \cdot a71$	$2^5/5 \cdot a72$	$2^5/5 \cdot a73$	$2^5/5 \cdot a74$	$2^5/5 \cdot a75$	$2^5/5 \cdot a76$	$2^5/5 \cdot a77$	$2^5/5 \cdot a78$	$2^5/5 \cdot a79$	$2^5/5 \cdot a80$	$2^5/5 \cdot a81$	$2^5/5 \cdot a82$	$a76 + a74 + a75 + a73 + a72 + a71 + a70 + a69 + a82 + a81 + a80 + a79 + a78 + a77 - (13/5) \cdot S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a84$	a84	
$3^5 \cdot a113 - a114 + a83 - a84 - 2^5 \cdot a110 - a116 - a115 - a117 - a118 - a120 - a119 - a121 - a112 - a111 - a122$	$a113 + a114 + a84 + 2^5 \cdot a110 - a83 + a116 + a115 + a117 + a118 + a120 + a119 + a121 + a112 + a111 + a122 - (13/5) \cdot S$	a31	a32	a33	a34	a35	a36	a37	a38	a39	a40	$(11/5) \cdot S - a31 - a32 - a34 - a35 - a36 - a37 - a38 - a39 - a40 - a33$	$2^5/5 \cdot a41$	a41	$2^5/5 \cdot a85$	a85	
a122	$2^5/5 \cdot a122$	$2^5/5 \cdot a31$	$2^5/5 \cdot a32$	$2^5/5 \cdot a33$	$2^5/5 \cdot a34$	$2^5/5 \cdot a35$	$2^5/5 \cdot a36$	$2^5/5 \cdot a37$	$2^5/5 \cdot a38$	$2^5/5 \cdot a39$	$2^5/5 \cdot a40$	$a31 + a32 + a34 + a35 + a36 + a37 + a38 + a39 + a40 + a33 - (9/5) \cdot S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a42$	a42	$2^5/5 \cdot a86$	a86	
a121	$2^5/5 \cdot a121$	$(11/5) \cdot S + a41 - a42 - 2^5 \cdot a60 - a62 - a63 - a64 - a65 - a66 - a67 - a68 - a61$	$a42 + 2^5 \cdot a60 - a41 + a62 + a63 + a64 + a65 + a66 + a67 + a68 + a61 - (9/5) \cdot S$	a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	$(7/5) \cdot S - a9 - a10 - a11 - a12 - a13 - a14$	$2^5/5 \cdot a15$	a15	$2^5/5 \cdot a43$	a43	$2^5/5 \cdot a87$	a87	
a120	$2^5/5 \cdot a120$	a68	$2^5/5 \cdot a68$	$2^5/5 \cdot a9$	$2^5/5 \cdot a10$	$2^5/5 \cdot a11$	$2^5/5 \cdot a12$	$2^5/5 \cdot a13$	$2^5/5 \cdot a14$	$a9 + a10 + a11 + a12 + a13 + a14 - S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a16$	a16	$2^5/5 \cdot a44$	a44	$2^5/5 \cdot a88$	a88	
a119	$2^5/5 \cdot a119$	a67	$2^5/5 \cdot a67$	$(7/5) \cdot S - a30 - a29 - a28 - a27 - 2^5 \cdot a26 + a15 - a16$	$a30 + a29 + a28 + a27 + 2^5 \cdot a26 - a15 - a16 - S$	a1	a2	$S - a1 - a2 - a3 - a4$	a3	a4	$2^5/5 \cdot a17$	a17	$2^5/5 \cdot a45$	a45	$2^5/5 \cdot a89$	a89	
a118	$2^5/5 \cdot a118$	a66	$2^5/5 \cdot a66$	a30	$2^5/5 \cdot a30$	$a8 - a2 + a7$	a5	$a1 + a2 + a3 + a4 - a5 - a6 - a7$	a6	$S - a1 - a3 - a4 - a8$	$2^5/5 \cdot a18$	a18	$2^5/5 \cdot a46$	a46	$2^5/5 \cdot a90$	a90	
a117	$2^5/5 \cdot a117$	a65	$2^5/5 \cdot a65$	a29	$2^5/5 \cdot a29$	$a2 + a3 + a4 - a5 - a7$	$S - a1 - a2 - a3 - a4 + a6 - a8$	a7	$a7 - a2 - a3 + a5 + a8$	$a1 + a2 + a3 - a6 - a7$	$2^5/5 \cdot a19$	a19	$2^5/5 \cdot a47$	a47	$2^5/5 \cdot a91$	a91	
a116	$2^5/5 \cdot a116$	a64	$2^5/5 \cdot a64$	a28	$2^5/5 \cdot a28$	$a7 - a3 + a5$	$a1 - a6 + a8$	$a2 + a3 - a7$	$S - a1 - a5 - a7 - a8$	$a7 - a2 + a6$	$2^5/5 \cdot a20$	a20	$2^5/5 \cdot a48$	a48	$2^5/5 \cdot a92$	a92	
a115	$2^5/5 \cdot a115$	a63	$2^5/5 \cdot a63$	a27	$2^5/5 \cdot a27$	$S - a1 - a4 - a7 - a8$	$a3 + a4 - a5$	$a7 - a2 - a3 + a5 + a6$	$a1 + a2 - a6$	a8	$a15 + a16 + a17 + a18 + a19 + a20 - S$	$(7/5) \cdot S - a15 - a16 - a17 - a18 - a19 - a20$	$2^5/5 \cdot a49$	a49	$2^5/5 \cdot a93$	a93	
a114	$2^5/5 \cdot a114$	a62	$2^5/5 \cdot a62$	a26	$2^5/5 \cdot a26$	$a25 + a24 + a23 + a22 + 2^5 \cdot a21 - a9 + a10 - S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a25$	$2^5/5 \cdot a24$	$2^5/5 \cdot a23$	$2^5/5 \cdot a22$	$2^5/5 \cdot a21$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a9 - a10 - a21$	$2^5/5 \cdot a50$	a50	$2^5/5 \cdot a94$	a94	
a113	$2^5/5 \cdot a113$	a61	$2^5/5 \cdot a61$	$a16 + a26 - a15$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a15 - a16 - a26$	$(7/5) \cdot S - a25 - a24 - a23 - a22 - 2^5 \cdot a21 + a9 - a10$	a25	a24	a23	a22	a21	$a10 + a21 - a9$	$a42 + a41 + a50 + a49 + a48 + a47 + a46 + a45 + a44 + a43 - (9/5) \cdot S$	$(11/5) \cdot S - a42 - a41 - a50 - a49 - a48 - a47 - a46 - a45 - a44 - a43$	$2^5/5 \cdot a95$	a95	
a112	$2^5/5 \cdot a112$	a60	$2^5/5 \cdot a60$	$a32 + 2^5 \cdot a51 - a31 + a52 + a53 + a54 + a55 + a56 + a57 + a58 + a59 - (9/5) \cdot S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a59$	$2^5/5 \cdot a58$	$2^5/5 \cdot a57$	$2^5/5 \cdot a56$	$2^5/5 \cdot a55$	$2^5/5 \cdot a54$	$2^5/5 \cdot a53$	$2^5/5 \cdot a52$	$2^5/5 \cdot a51$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a31 - a32 - a51$	$2^5/5 \cdot a96$	a96	
a111	$2^5/5 \cdot a111$	$a42 + a60 - a41$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a41 - a42 - a60$	$(11/5) \cdot S + a31 - a32 - 2^5 \cdot a51 - a52 - a53 - a54 - a55 - a56 - a57 - a58 - a59$	a59	a58	a57	a56	a55	a54	a53	a52	a51	$a32 + a51 - a31$	$a96 + a95 + a94 + a91 + a90 + a89 + a88 + a87 + a86 + a85 + a84 + a83 + a93 + a92 - (13/5) \cdot S$	$3^5 \cdot a96 - a95 - a94 - a91 - a90 - a89 - a88 - a87 - a86 - a85 - a84 - a83 - a93 - a92$	a96
a110	$2^5/5 \cdot a110$	$a108 + a107 + a109 + a99 + a98 + 2^5 \cdot a97 + a106 + a104 + a105 + a101 + a102 + a103 + a100 - a69 + a70 - (13/5) \cdot S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a109$	$2^5/5 \cdot a108$	$2^5/5 \cdot a107$	$2^5/5 \cdot a106$	$2^5/5 \cdot a105$	$2^5/5 \cdot a104$	$2^5/5 \cdot a103$	$2^5/5 \cdot a102$	$2^5/5 \cdot a101$	$2^5/5 \cdot a100$	$2^5/5 \cdot a99$	$2^5/5 \cdot a98$	$2^5/5 \cdot a97$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a69 - a70 - a97$	a97
$a84 + a110 - a83$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a83 - a84 - a110$	a109	a108	a107	a106	a105	a104	a103	a102	a101	a100	a99	a98	a97	a96	$a70 + a97 - a69$	a96

• Details

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×7 , 2×11 and 2×15 (equality in each case) embedded with a pandiagonal magic square of order 5. The magic square of order 5 don't requires any condition but the magic sums of orders 17, 13 and 9 depends on five. Thus, we must have these magic sums as multiples of 5 to avoid decimal entries. The magic sum of orders 17, 13 and 9 are given as $S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{17S}{5}$, $S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13S}{5}$, and $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$, where S is the magic sum of order 5.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.15

Example 2.11. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.15:

17	mgc	17x17	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	289												
	205	208	211	214	217	220	223	226	229	232	235	238	241	244	-2888	-213	247	289
	-171	-174	-177	-180	-183	-186	-189	-192	-195	-198	-201	-204	-207	-210	2922	-216	250	289
	-4574	4608	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	-858	-87	121	-219	253	289
	364	-330	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	892	-90	124	-222	256	289
	361	-327	-1704	1738	25	28	31	34	37	40	-76	-9	43	-93	127	-225	259	289
	358	-324	202	-168	9	6	3	0	-3	-6	110	-12	46	-96	130	-228	262	289
	355	-321	199	-165	-370	404	1	4	63	7	10	-15	49	-99	133	-231	265	289
	352	-318	196	-162	88	-54	37	13	-26	16	45	-18	52	-102	136	-234	268	289
	349	-315	193	-159	85	-51	-11	57	19	43	-23	-21	55	-105	139	-237	271	289
	346	-312	190	-156	82	-48	25	7	-8	30	31	-24	58	-108	142	-240	274	289
	343	-309	187	-153	79	-45	33	4	37	-11	22	218	-184	-111	145	-243	277	289
	340	-306	184	-150	76	-42	314	-39	-36	-33	-30	-27	-30	-114	148	-246	280	289
	337	-303	181	-147	79	-45	-280	73	70	67	64	61	64	1192	-1158	-249	283	289
	334	-300	178	-144	1468	-141	-138	-135	-132	-129	-126	-123	-120	-117	-120	-252	286	289
	331	-297	181	-147	-1434	175	172	169	166	163	160	157	154	151	154	3510	-3476	289
	328	-294	4062	-291	-288	-285	-282	-279	-276	-273	-270	-267	-264	-261	-258	-255	-258	289
	331	-297	-4028	325	322	319	316	313	310	307	304	301	298	295	292	289	292	289
	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289

and

17	mgc	17x17	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	357												
	205	208	211	214	217	220	223	226	229	232	235	238	241	244	-2828	-205	247	357
	-163	-166	-169	-172	-175	-178	-181	-184	-187	-190	-193	-196	-199	-202	2870	-208	250	357
	-4514	4556	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	-814	-79	121	-211	253	357
	364	-322	-49	-52	-55	-58	-61	-64	-67	-70	-73	-76	856	-82	124	-214	256	357
	361	-319	-1660	1702	25	28	31	34	37	40	-48	-1	43	-85	127	-217	259	357
	358	-316	202	-160	17	14	11	8	5	2	90	-4	46	-88	130	-220	262	357
	355	-313	199	-157	-342	384	1	4	83	7	10	-7	49	-91	133	-223	265	357
	352	-310	196	-154	88	-46	37	13	-26	16	65	-10	52	-94	136	-226	268	357
	349	-307	193	-151	85	-43	-11	77	19	43	-23	-13	55	-97	139	-229	271	357
	346	-304	190	-148	82	-40	25	7	-8	50	31	-16	58	-100	142	-232	274	357
	343	-301	187	-145	79	-37	53	4	37	-11	22	198	-156	-103	145	-235	277	357
	340	-298	184	-142	76	-34	294	-31	-28	-25	-22	-19	-22	-106	148	-238	280	357
	337	-295	181	-139	79	-37	-252	73	70	67	64	61	64	1156	-1114	-241	283	357
	334	-292	178	-136	1432	-133	-130	-127	-124	-121	-118	-115	-112	-109	-112	-244	286	357
	331	-289	181	-139	-1390	175	172	169	166	163	160	157	154	151	154	3458	-3416	357
	328	-286	4010	-283	-280	-277	-274	-271	-268	-265	-262	-259	-256	-253	-250	-247	-250	357
	331	-289	-3968	325	322	319	316	313	310	307	304	301	298	295	292	289	292	357
	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{5 \times 5} := 85$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 153$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 221$ and $S_{17 \times 17} := 289$.
- Second example: $S_{5 \times 5} := 105$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 189$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 273$ and $S_{17 \times 17} := 357$.

2.12 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 18

Result 2.16. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 18 with reduced entries:*

a77	a78	a79	a80	a81	a82	a83	a84	a85	a86	a87	a88	a89	a90	a91	(16/3)*S-a91-a90-a89-a88-a87-a86-a85-a84-a83-a82-a81-a80-a79-a78-a77	(2/3)*S-a92	a92	
(2/3)*S-a77	(2/3)*S-a78	(2/3)*S-a79	(2/3)*S-a80	(2/3)*S-a81	(2/3)*S-a82	(2/3)*S-a83	(2/3)*S-a84	(2/3)*S-a85	(2/3)*S-a86	(2/3)*S-a87	(2/3)*S-a88	(2/3)*S-a89	(2/3)*S-a90	(2/3)*S-a91	a91+a90+a89+a88+a87+a86+a85+a84+a83+a82+a81+a80+a79+a78+a77-(14/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a93	a93	
(16/3)*S-a134-a133-a132-a131-a130-a129-a128-a127+a92-a93-2*a121-a123-a122-a126-a125-a124	a134+a133+a132+a131+a130+a129+a128+a127+a93+2*a121-a92+a123+a122+a126+a125+a124-(14/3)*S															(2/3)*S-a94	a94	
a134	(2/3)*S-a134																(2/3)*S-a95	a95
a133	(2/3)*S-a133																(2/3)*S-a96	a96
a132	(2/3)*S-a132																(2/3)*S-a97	a97
a131	(2/3)*S-a131																(2/3)*S-a98	a98
a130	(2/3)*S-a130																(2/3)*S-a99	a99
a129	(2/3)*S-a129																(2/3)*S-a100	a100
a128	(2/3)*S-a128																(2/3)*S-a101	a101
a127	(2/3)*S-a127																(2/3)*S-a102	a102
a126	(2/3)*S-a126																(2/3)*S-a103	a103
a125	(2/3)*S-a125																(2/3)*S-a104	a104
a124	(2/3)*S-a124																(2/3)*S-a105	a105
a123	(2/3)*S-a123																(2/3)*S-a106	a106
a122	(2/3)*S-a122																a99+a98+a97+a96+a95+a106+a104+a105+a101+a102+a103+a100+a94+a93+a92-(14/3)*S	(16/3)*S-a99-a98-a97-a96-a95-a106-a104-a105-a101-a102-a103-a100-a94-a93-a92
a121	(2/3)*S-a121	a113+a114+a116+a115+a117+a118+a120+a119+a108+2*a107+a109+a110+a112+a111-a77+a78-(14/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a120	(2/3)*S-a119	(2/3)*S-a118	(2/3)*S-a117	(2/3)*S-a116	(2/3)*S-a115	(2/3)*S-a114	(2/3)*S-a113	(2/3)*S-a112	(2/3)*S-a111	(2/3)*S-a110	(2/3)*S-a109	(2/3)*S-a108	(2/3)*S-a107	(2/3)*S-a77-a78-a107	
a93+a121-a92	(2/3)*S+a92-a93-a121	(16/3)*S-a113-a114-a116-a115-a117-a118-a120-a119-a108-2*a107-a109-a110-a112-a111+a77-a78	a120	a119	a118	a117	a116	a115	a114	a113	a112	a111	a110	a109	a108	a107	a78+a107-a77	

The internal part is the exactly the same as given in the Result 2.12. The complete structure can be seen in a web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17009>.

• Details

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 , 2×12 and 2×16 (equal in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is again composed of four equal sums magic squares of order 3. Since the magic square of order 3 requires magic sum as multiple of 3, otherwise we may have decimal entries. The magic sums of orders 10, 14 and 18 are also multiple of 3. The magic sum of orders 10, 14 and 18 are given as $S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10S}{3}$, $S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14S}{3}$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := \frac{18S}{3} = 6S$, where S is the magic sum of order 3. In this case the magic sum of order 6 is given as $S_{6 \times 6} := 2S$.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.16

Example 2.12. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.16:

18	mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT														486			
	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	-828	-38	92	486
	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-35	-36	-37	882	-39	93	486
	-1475	1529	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	-116	8	46	-40	94	486
	134	-80	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	170	7	47	-41	95	486
	133	-79	-459	513	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	132	38	16	6	48	-42	96	486
	132	-78	76	-22	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	-78	37	17	5	49	-43	97	486
	131	-77	75	-21	-3	57	-24	52	53	-20	50	51	36	18	4	50	-44	98	486
	130	-76	74	-20	34	20	104	27	-50	98	27	-44	35	19	3	51	-45	99	486
	129	-75	73	-19	33	21	1	2	78	3	4	74	34	20	2	52	-46	100	486
	128	-74	72	-18	32	22	-16	48	49	-12	46	47	33	21	1	53	-47	101	486
	127	-73	71	-17	31	23	92	27	-38	86	27	-32	32	22	0	54	-48	102	486
	126	-72	70	-16	30	24	5	6	70	7	8	66	-29	83	-1	55	-49	103	486
	125	-71	69	-15	29	25	15	26	27	28	29	30	31	30	-2	56	-50	104	486
	124	-70	68	-14	30	24	39	28	27	26	25	24	23	24	291	-237	-51	105	486
	123	-69	67	-13	403	-12	-11	-10	-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-4	-52	106	486
	122	-68	68	-14	-349	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	58	1107	-1053	486
	121	-67	1319	-66	-65	-64	-63	-62	-61	-60	-59	-58	-57	-56	-55	-54	-53	-54	486
	122	-68	-1265	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	110	109	108	107	108	486
	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486	486

and

18	mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT														594			
	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	-732	-26	92	594
	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	798	-27	93	594
	-1379	1445	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	-44	20	46	-28	94	594
	134	-68	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	110	19	47	-29	95	594
	133	-67	-387	453	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	180	50	16	18	48	-30	96	594
	132	-66	76	-10	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	-114	49	17	17	49	-31	97	594
	131	-65	75	-9	45	21	-30	64	65	-26	62	63	48	18	16	50	-32	98	594
	130	-64	74	-8	34	32	128	33	-62	122	33	-56	47	19	15	51	-33	99	594
	129	-63	73	-7	33	33	1	2	96	3	4	92	46	20	14	52	-34	100	594
	128	-62	72	-6	32	34	-22	60	61	-18	58	59	45	21	13	53	-35	101	594
	127	-61	71	-5	31	35	116	33	-50	110	33	-44	44	22	12	54	-36	102	594
	126	-60	70	-4	30	36	5	6	88	7	8	84	-65	131	11	55	-37	103	594
	125	-59	69	-3	29	37	-21	38	39	40	41	42	43	42	10	56	-38	104	594
	124	-58	68	-2	30	36	87	28	27	26	25	24	23	24	231	-165	-39	105	594
	123	-57	67	-1	343	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	8	-40	106	594
	122	-56	68	-2	-277	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	58	1023	-957	594
	121	-55	1235	-54	-53	-52	-51	-50	-49	-48	-47	-46	-45	-44	-43	-42	-41	-42	594
	122	-56	-1169	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	110	109	108	107	108	594
	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594	594

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 81$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 162$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 270$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 378$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 486$.
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 99$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 198$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 330$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 462$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 594$.

2.13 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 19

Result 2.17. Let's consider a following magic square of order 19 with reduced entries:

a94	a95	a96	a97	a98	a99	a100	a101	a102	a103	a104	a105	a106	a107	a108	a109	(17/3)*S-a108-a107-a109-a99-a98-a97-a96-a95-a106-a104-a105-a101-a102-a103-a100-a94	2*S/3-a110	a110	
2*S/3-a94	2*S/3-a95	2*S/3-a96	2*S/3-a97	2*S/3-a98	2*S/3-a99	2*S/3-a100	2*S/3-a101	2*S/3-a102	2*S/3-a103	2*S/3-a104	2*S/3-a105	2*S/3-a106	2*S/3-a107	2*S/3-a108	2*S/3-a109	a108+a107+a109+a99+a98+a97+a96+a95+a106+a104+a105+a101+a102+a103+a100+a94-5*S	2*S/3-a111	a111	
(17/3)*S-a145-a144-a143-a149-a148-a147-a146+a110-a111-2*a141-a152-a151-a150-a155-a154-a153-a142	a145+a144+a143+a149+a148+a147+a146+a111+2*a141-a110+a152+a151+a150+a155+a154+a153+a142-5*S																2*S/3-a112	a112	
a155	2*S/3-a155																2*S/3-a113	a113	
a154	2*S/3-a154																2*S/3-a114	a114	
a153	2*S/3-a153																2*S/3-a115	a115	
a152	2*S/3-a152																2*S/3-a116	a116	
a151	2*S/3-a151																2*S/3-a117	a117	
a150	2*S/3-a150																2*S/3-a118	a118	
a149	2*S/3-a149																2*S/3-a119	a119	
a148	2*S/3-a148																2*S/3-a120	a120	
a147	2*S/3-a147																2*S/3-a121	a121	
a146	2*S/3-a146																2*S/3-a122	a122	
a145	2*S/3-a145																2*S/3-a123	a123	
a144	2*S/3-a144																2*S/3-a124	a124	
a143	2*S/3-a143																2*S/3-a125	a125	
a142	2*S/3-a142																a113+a114+a116+a115+a117+a118+a120+a119+a121+a110+a112+a111+a123+a122+a125+a124-5*S	(17/3)*S-a113-a114-a115-a117-a118-a120-a119-a121-a110-2+a111-a123-a122-a125-a124	a125-a124
a141	2*S/3-a141	a140+a139+a138+a137+a136+a135+a134+a133+a132+a131+a130+a129+a128+a127+2*a126-a94+a95-5*S	2*S/3-a140	2*S/3-a139	2*S/3-a138	2*S/3-a137	2*S/3-a136	2*S/3-a135	2*S/3-a134	2*S/3-a133	2*S/3-a132	2*S/3-a131	2*S/3-a130	2*S/3-a129	2*S/3-a128	2*S/3-a127	2*S/3-a126	(2/3)*S+a94-a95-a126	
a111+a141-a110	(2/3)*S+a110-a111-a141	(17/3)*S-a140-a139-a138-a137-a136-a135-a134-a133-a132-a131-a130-a129-a128-a127-2*a126+a94-a95	a140	a139	a138	a137	a136	a135	a134	a133	a132	a131	a130	a129	a128	a127	a126	a95+a126-a94	

The internal part is the exactly the same as given in the Result 2.13. The complete structure can be seen in a web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17009>.

• **Details**

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×5 , 2×9 , 2×13 and 2×17 (equality in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 3. Since the magic square of order 3 requires magic sum as multiple of 3, otherwise we have decimal entries, then the magic sums of orders 7, 11, 15 and 19 are also multiples of 3. The magic sum of orders 7, 11, 15 and 19 are given as $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$, $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$, $S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15S}{3} = 5S$ and $S_{19 \times 19} := \frac{19S}{3}$ where S is the magic sum of order 3.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.17

Example 2.13. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.17:

19	mgc	19x19 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT																	1235	
	281	284	287	290	293	296	299	302	305	308	311	314	317	320	323	326	-3751	-199	329	1235
	-151	-154	-157	-160	-163	-166	-169	-172	-175	-178	-181	-184	-187	-190	-193	-196	3881	-202	332	1235
	-5965	6095	143	146	149	152	155	158	161	164	167	170	173	176	-1069	-49	179	-205	335	1235
	464	-334	-13	-16	-19	-22	-25	-28	-31	-34	-37	-40	-43	-46	1199	-52	182	-208	338	1235
	461	-331	-2299	2429	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	101	56	74	-55	185	-211	341	1235
	458	-328	278	-148	80	77	74	71	68	65	62	59	29	53	77	-58	188	-214	344	1235
	455	-325	275	-145	-457	587	8	11	14	17	275	110	20	50	80	-61	191	-217	347	1235
	452	-322	272	-142	140	-10	122	119	116	113	-145	107	23	47	83	-64	194	-220	350	1235
	449	-319	269	-139	137	-7	149	-19	-58	125	128	104	26	44	86	-67	197	-223	353	1235
	446	-316	266	-136	134	-4	47	83	251	65	-121	101	29	41	89	-70	200	-226	356	1235
	443	-313	263	-133	131	-1	44	86	2	5	188	-97	227	38	92	-73	203	-229	359	1235
	440	-310	260	-130	128	2	41	89	-55	92	95	98	95	35	95	-76	206	-232	362	1235
	437	-307	257	-127	125	5	44	86	185	38	35	32	35	221	-91	-79	209	-235	365	1235
	434	-304	254	-124	122	8	395	14	17	20	23	26	29	32	29	-82	212	-238	368	1235
	431	-301	251	-121	125	5	-265	116	113	110	107	104	101	98	101	1631	-1501	-241	371	1235
	428	-298	248	-118	2033	-115	-112	-109	-106	-103	-100	-97	-94	-91	-88	-85	-88	-244	374	1235
	425	-295	251	-121	-1903	245	242	239	236	233	230	227	224	221	218	215	218	4649	-4519	1235
	422	-292	5375	-289	-286	-283	-280	-277	-274	-271	-268	-265	-262	-259	-256	-253	-250	-247	-250	1235
	425	-295	-5245	419	416	413	410	407	404	401	398	395	392	389	386	383	380	377	380	1235
	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235

and

19	mgc	19x19 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT																	1254		
		281	284	287	290	293	296	299	302	305	308	311	314	317	320	323	326	-3734	-197	329	1254
		-149	-152	-155	-158	-161	-164	-167	-170	-173	-176	-179	-182	-185	-188	-191	-194	3866	-200	332	1254
	-5948 6080	143	146	149	152	155	158	161	164	167	170	173	176	-1056	-47	179	-203	335	1254		
	464 -332	-11	-14	-17	-20	-23	-26	-29	-32	-35	-38	-41	-44	1188	-50	182	-206	338	1254		
	461 -329	-2286	2418	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	110	58	74	-53	185	-209	341	1254		
	458 -326	278	-146	82	79	76	73	70	67	64	61	22	55	77	-56	188	-212	344	1254		
	455 -323	275	-143	-448	580	8	11	14	17	280	112	20	52	80	-59	191	-215	347	1254		
	452 -320	272	-140	140	-8	124	121	118	115	-148	109	23	49	83	-62	194	-218	350	1254		
	449 -317	269	-137	137	-5	154	-22	-59	127	130	106	26	46	86	-65	197	-221	353	1254		
	446 -314	266	-134	134	-2	47	85	255	66	-123	103	29	43	89	-68	200	-224	356	1254		
	443 -311	263	-131	131	1	44	88	2	5	191	-100	232	40	92	-71	203	-227	359	1254		
	440 -308	260	-128	128	4	41	91	-58	94	97	100	97	37	95	-74	206	-230	362	1254		
	437 -305	257	-125	125	7	44	88	190	38	35	32	35	214	-82	-77	209	-233	365	1254		
	434 -302	254	-122	122	10	388	16	19	22	25	28	31	34	31	-80	212	-236	368	1254		
	431 -299	251	-119	125	7	-256	116	113	110	107	104	101	98	101	1620	-1488	-239	371	1254		
	428 -296	248	-116	2022	-113	-110	-107	-104	-101	-98	-95	-92	-89	-86	-83	-86	-242	374	1254		
	425 -293	251	-119	-1890	245	242	239	236	233	230	227	224	221	218	215	218	4634	-4502	1254		
	422 -290	5360	-287	-284	-281	-278	-275	-272	-269	-266	-263	-260	-257	-254	-251	-248	-245	-248	1254		
	425 -293	-5228	419	416	413	410	407	404	401	398	395	392	389	386	383	380	377	380	1254		
		1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 195$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 455$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 715$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 975$ and $S_{19 \times 19} := 1235$.
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 198$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 462$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 726$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 990$ and $S_{19 \times 19} := 1254$.

2.14 Double-Digit Bordered Algebraic Magic Square of Order 20

Result 2.18. *Let's consider a following magic square of order 20 with reduced entries:*

a109	a110	a111	a112	a113	a114	a115	a116	a117	a118	a119	a120	a121	a122	a123	a124	a125	(9/2)*S-a125-a123-a124-a121-a122-a120	S/2-a126	a126	
S/2-a109	S/2-a110	S/2-a111	S/2-a112	S/2-a113	S/2-a114	S/2-a115	S/2-a116	S/2-a117	S/2-a118	S/2-a119	S/2-a120	S/2-a121	S/2-a122	S/2-a123	S/2-a124	S/2-a125	a125+a123+a124+a121+a122+a120+a118+a119+a116+a117+a114+a115-a112-a113-a111-a109-a110	S/2-a127	a127	
(9/2)*S-2*a159+a126-a127-a162-a161-a160-a166-a165-a164-a163-a169-a168-a167-a173-a172-a171-a170-a174	2*a159-a126+a127+a162+a161+a160+a166+a165+a164+a163+a169+a168+a167+a173+a172+a171+a170+a174-4*S																	S/2-a128	a128	
a174	S/2-a174																	S/2-a129	a129	
a173	S/2-a173																	S/2-a130	a130	
a172	S/2-a172																	S/2-a131	a131	
a171	S/2-a171																	S/2-a132	a132	
a170	S/2-a170																	S/2-a133	a133	
a169	S/2-a169																	S/2-a134	a134	
a168	S/2-a168																	S/2-a135	a135	
a167	S/2-a167																	S/2-a136	a136	
a166	S/2-a166																	S/2-a137	a137	
a165	S/2-a165																	S/2-a138	a138	
a164	S/2-a164																	S/2-a139	a139	
a163	S/2-a163																	S/2-a140	a140	
a162	S/2-a162																	S/2-a141	a141	
a161	S/2-a161																	S/2-a142	a142	
a160	S/2-a160																	a140+a141+a142+a136+a137+a138+a139+a133+a134+a135+a129+a130+a131+a132+a126+a127+a128-4*S	(9/2)*S-a140-a141-a142-a136-a137-a138-a139-a133-a134-a135-a129-a130-a131-a132-a126-a127-a128	
a159	S/2-a159	a158+a157+a156+a155+a154+a153+a110+2*a143-a109+a144+a145+a147+a146+a149+a148+a151+a150+a152-4*S	S/2-a158	S/2-a157	S/2-a156	S/2-a155	S/2-a154	S/2-a153	S/2-a152	S/2-a151	S/2-a150	S/2-a149	S/2-a148	S/2-a147	S/2-a146	S/2-a145	S/2-a144	S/2-a143	(1/2)*S+a109-a110-a143	
a127+a159-a126	(1/2)*S+a126-a127-a159	(9/2)*S-a158-a157-a156-a155-a154-a153+a109-a110-2*a143-a144-a145-a147-a146-a149-a148-a151-a150-a152	a158	a157	a156	a155	a154	a153	a152	a151	a150	a149	a148	a147	a146	a145	a144	a143	a110+a143-a109	

The internal part is the exactly the same as given in the Result 2.14. The complete structure can be seen in a web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17009>.

• **Details**

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×6 , 2×10 , 2×14 and 2×18 (equality in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 4. Since the magic square of order 4 requires magic sum as multiple of 2, otherwise we have decimal entries, then the magic sum of orders, 8, 12 and 16 are also multiple of 2. The magic sum of orders 20, 16, 12 and 8 are given as $S_{20 \times 20} := 5S$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 4S$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 3S$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 2S$, where S is the magic sum of order 4.

Below are two examples based on the Result 2.18

Example 2.14. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.18:

20	mgc	20x20 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																		510	
	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	-1547	-76	127	510
	-59	-60	-61	-62	-63	-64	-65	-66	-67	-68	-69	-70	-71	-72	-73	-74	-75	1598	-77	128	510
	-2382	2433	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	-501	-22	73	-78	129	510
	175	-124	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	552	-23	74	-79	130	510
	174	-123	-984	1035	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	-15	16	35	-24	75	-80	131	510
	173	-122	109	-58	25	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	66	15	36	-25	76	-81	132	510
	172	-121	108	-57	-242	293	8	9	10	11	12	103	38	13	14	37	-26	77	-82	133	510
	171	-120	107	-56	59	-8	43	42	41	40	39	-52	37	14	13	38	-27	78	-83	134	510
	170	-119	106	-55	58	-7	36	15	2	98	-2	4	36	15	12	39	-28	79	-84	135	510
	169	-118	105	-54	57	-6	25	26	7	5	6	84	35	16	11	40	-29	80	-85	136	510
	168	-117	104	-53	56	-5	24	27	0	-1	92	11	34	17	10	41	-30	81	-86	137	510
	167	-116	103	-52	55	-4	23	28	93	0	6	3	-27	78	9	42	-31	82	-87	138	510
	166	-115	102	-51	54	-3	22	29	-5	30	31	32	33	32	8	43	-32	83	-88	139	510
	165	-114	101	-50	53	-2	23	28	56	21	20	19	18	19	147	-96	-33	84	-89	140	510
	164	-113	100	-49	52	-1	221	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	6	-34	85	-90	141	510
	163	-112	99	-48	53	-2	-170	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	45	721	-670	-91	142	510
	162	-111	98	-47	879	-46	-45	-44	-43	-42	-41	-40	-39	-38	-37	-36	-35	-36	-92	143	510
	161	-110	99	-48	-828	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	87	1887	-1836	510
	160	-109	2161	-108	-107	-106	-105	-104	-103	-102	-101	-100	-99	-98	-97	-96	-95	-94	-93	-94	510
	161	-110	-2110	159	158	157	156	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	145	510
	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510

and

20	mgc	20x20 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																		760	
	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	-1322	-51	127	760
	-34	-35	-36	-37	-38	-39	-40	-41	-42	-43	-44	-45	-46	-47	-48	-49	-50	1398	-52	128	760
	-2157	2233	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	-326	3	73	-53	129	760
	175	-99	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	402	2	74	-54	130	760
	174	-98	-809	885	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	110	41	35	1	75	-55	131	760
	173	-97	109	-33	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	-34	40	36	0	76	-56	132	760
	172	-96	108	-32	-117	193	8	9	10	11	12	178	63	13	39	37	-1	77	-57	133	760
	171	-95	107	-31	59	17	68	67	66	65	64	-102	62	14	38	38	-2	78	-58	134	760
	170	-94	106	-30	58	18	111	-35	2	148	-2	4	61	15	37	39	-3	79	-59	135	760
	169	-93	105	-29	57	19	25	51	7	5	6	134	60	16	36	40	-4	80	-60	136	760
	168	-92	104	-28	56	20	24	52	0	-1	142	11	59	17	35	41	-5	81	-61	137	760
	167	-91	103	-27	55	21	23	53	143	0	6	3	-77	153	34	42	-6	82	-62	138	760
	166	-90	102	-26	54	22	22	54	-55	55	56	57	58	57	33	43	-7	83	-63	139	760
	165	-89	101	-25	53	23	23	53	131	21	20	19	18	19	47	29	-8	84	-64	140	760
	164	-88	100	-24	52	24	121	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	31	-9	85	-65	141	760
	163	-87	99	-23	53	23	-45	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	45	571	-495	-66	142	760
	162	-86	98	-22	729	-21	-20	-19	-18	-17	-16	-15	-14	-13	-12	-11	-10	-11	-67	143	760
	161	-85	99	-23	-653	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	87	1687	-1611	760
	160	-84	1961	-83	-82	-81	-80	-79	-78	-77	-76	-75	-74	-73	-72	-71	-70	-69	-68	-69	760
	161	-85	-1885	159	158	157	156	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	145	760
	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760	760

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 102$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 204$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 312$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 408$ and $S_{20 \times 20} := 510$.
- Second example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 152$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 304$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 456$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 608$ and $S_{20 \times 20} := 760$.

3 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author’s contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

References

- [1] **A. de Winkel**, The magic Encyclopedia, <http://home.wanadoo.nl/aaledewinkel/Encyclopedia/index.html>
- [2] **C. Boyer**, Multimagic Squares and Cubes, <http://www.multimagie.com>
- [3] **F. Gaspalou**, "Magic Squares" <http://www.gaspalou.fr/magic-squares/>
- [4] **W. Trump**, <http://www.trump.de/magic-squares>
- [5] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
- [6] **W.S. Andrews**, Magic squares and Cubes, Dover Publications, New York

• Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares: Dates and Days of the Year

- [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7 Representing Dates and Days of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 04, 2025, pp. 1-474, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15338142>.
- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 8 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 04, 2025, pp. 1-134, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15338246>.
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 9 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 09, 2025, pp. 1-132, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15375349>.
- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 10 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 21, 2025, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15481738>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of order 11 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, June 02, 2025, pp. 1-111, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15576562>.
- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of order 12 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, June 10, 2025, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15631884>.

• Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares: Different Styles

- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reduced Entries Magic and Semi-Magic Squares of Orders 3, 5, 7 and 9, **Zenodo**, July 01, 2025, pp. 1-65, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15783321>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reduced Entries Magic and Semi-Magic Squares of Orders 4, 6, 8 and 10, **Zenodo**, July 05, 2025, pp. 1-85, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15814675>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7, **Zenodo**, September 29, 2025, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17219769>.
- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 8, **Zenodo**, September 23, 2025, pp. 1-65, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17186001>.
- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 9, **Zenodo**, August 27, 2025, pp. 1-92, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16955571>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 10, **Zenodo**, September 21, 2025, pp. 1-132, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17171790>.
- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 11, **Zenodo**, October 12, 2025, pp. 1-58, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17330815>.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 11, **Zenodo**, October 12, 2025, pp. 1-77, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17330822>.
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic and PanMagic Squares of Order 12, **Zenodo**, July 23, 2025, pp. 1-74, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16370556>.
- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reduced Entries Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 12, **Zenodo**, July 23, 2025, pp. 1-60, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15692014>.
- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double-Digit Cyclic-Type Bordered Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 20, **Zenodo**, November 21, 2025, pp. 1-37, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17675032>.

• Double-Digit Magic Squares

- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880931>.
- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880937>.

- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40, **Zenodo**, May, 04, 2023, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7896709>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 34 and 38, **Zenodo**, May 10, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922571>.
- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866981>.
- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866956>.
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.
-